

Green Human Resource Management Practices at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company

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Abstract

Green human resource management requires changes in the culture, structure, strategy and regulations of health human resource management to promote environmental sustainability. That contributes to the sustainable development of organizations. Purpose: To evaluate the role of green human resource management practices in achieving the development of Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company. The study was conducted at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company with a survey of 135 officers and employees of the company. Based on the survey and analysis of the research results, the author proposed a number of solutions to improve green human resource management at this company.

Keywords: *Green human resource management, Thai Think hospital joint stock company.*

JEL Classification codes: *F64, O15.*

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Introduction

In recent decades, the issue of environmental protection has emerged as one of the most pressing concerns worldwide. This issue has created more pressure and motivated business organizations to develop and adopt green management by adopting environmentally friendly processes and practices (Chaudhary, R., 2020). To achieve this development, many organizations are trying to create and implement an environmental management system. This system has been recognized as one of the most valuable keys to achieving sustainable development since the 1990s (Wibisono, Nurhatisyah, & Gustiawan, 2018). Environmental management has been integrated into several departments, such as: operations, finance, marketing and others (Wibisono, Nurhatisyah, & Gustiawan, 2018).

Recently, human resource management has joined the green movement (Prathima and Misra, 2012). Human resource management is considered as the most important asset of the company that can integrate all activities together to achieve positive performance (Rawashdeh, 2018). Since it plays a vital role in achieving sustainable development in organizations, many scholars have turned their attention to the relationship between human resources and environmental

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management, as they have affirmed the importance of green practices for employees in the company (Wibisono, Nurhatsiyah, & Gustiawan, 2018). This link between human resource management and environmental management is called green human resource management which aims to support companies to stimulate environmental performance through improving employee commitment to the environment (Schuler and Jackson, 2014; Al Mamun, M. A., 2019; Renwick, 2013; Wibisono, Nurhatsiyah, & Gustiawan, 2018). Opatha and Arulrajah (2014) define green human resource management as the policies, practices and systems of a company that help its employees to be active and proactive in realizing the benefits of people, business, society and the natural environment.

Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company was established on July 16, 2004, with the motto "For community health", the clinic and hospital complex was officially established and put into operation with 6 specialized departments: Internal Medicine - Pediatrics, Obstetrics, Ultrasound, Laboratory, X-ray, ENT, meeting the diverse medical examination and treatment needs of the community. After many years of operation, besides the achievements in management, especially human resource management according to new trends to meet the sustainable development of the enterprise, there are still limitations such as in recruitment, training, treatment, creating motivation for employees, especially in influencing the behavior of employees in environmental protection.

On that basis, it is necessary to conduct research on the impact of green human resource management on the environmentally friendly behavior of hospital staff. Therefore, the author chose the issue of "Research on green human resource management at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company" as the research topic.

Some Basic Issues on Green Human Resource Management in Enterprises

Green Human Resource Management

According to Opatha (2014), "Green human resource management is the integration of environmental management into management". Prasad (2013) briefly defines: "Green human resource management is the contribution of human resource policies to protect natural resources".

From the above definitions, the author defines the concept of green human resource management: "Green human resource management is a set of human resource management activities aimed at creating, stimulating and developing environmentally responsible behavior of human resources to create an environmentally friendly workplace, contributing to achieving the goals of environmental protection and sustainable development of organizations and enterprises".

Activities to stimulate green behavior and environmentally responsible behavior of human resources are integrated into human resource management activities. These activities are implemented synchronously and uniformly to create direct stimulating effects, which are: Recruiting green human resources; Training green human resources; Evaluating green human resources; Treating green human resources.

1. Green human resource recruitment

First of all, to recruit green human resources into operation, as a basis to increase the opportunity to attract talented green candidates and retain them after applying, green job design as a basis and a fundamental activity that affects other activities of human resource management is also paid attention to.

Recruiting green human resources is a necessity for green and sustainable human resource management of enterprises. The recruitment process is in line with "environmentally friendly"

issues and makes it a key factor in the enterprise. Recruiting green-minded and aware workers makes it easier and more convenient for enterprises to introduce workers to the processes and familiarize them with basic issues such as recycling, conservation, etc. (Mishra, 2017).

2. Green human resource training

Combining the idea of green business in sustainable enterprises with the theory of human resource training "is the process of perfecting and enhancing the capacity of employees to meet the requirements of the job" (Mai Thanh Lan and Nguyen Thi Lien, 2022), thus, it can be understood that "Green human resource training at enterprises is the process of providing employees with different knowledge and values about environmental protection; cultivating skills, methods and training, spreading awareness, consciousness of saving energy, reducing waste, creating opportunities for employees to participate in environmental issues at enterprises".

3. Green human resource assessment

Evaluating green human resources in enterprises is understood as evaluating human resources in conjunction with green assessment criteria at work. Enterprises conduct amendments to the employee evaluation ranking system in conjunction with behavioral competencies and green work skills. Such competencies will further strengthen the core values of the enterprise. Managers conduct evaluations of employees' work performance through implementation and environmental protection actions.

4. Green human resource treatment

Human resource treatment is an important content of human resource management because the motivation of employees is directly affected by human resource treatment. This content refers to "the actual treatment and treatment of enterprises towards employees during their work" (Mai Thanh Lan and Nguyen Thi Minh Nhan, 2016). Thus, human resource treatment is a process that has influence over the entire working process of employees. Integrating human resource treatment with green initiatives can be understood as "Green human resource treatment is the way businesses treat their human resources through salaries, rewards, and working environments for employees based on their green work performance".

Green Innovation and Environmental Efficiency

Green innovation of enterprises refers to the use of novelty in products, production processes, business methods to prevent or minimize pollution, negative impacts on the environment due to resource use. Green innovation refers to product innovation (increasing the use of environmentally beneficial materials and fuels such as natural materials, low energy consumption, easy to recycle, reuse...) and process innovation (for example, improving processes to minimize waste, reduce electricity and water consumption...) (Singh et al., 2020). Along with that, marketing innovation, using "environmentally friendly" marketing methods (for example, limiting the printing and distribution of leaflets, limiting the use of flowers, increasing the communication of environmental messages, etc.) are also mentioned in green innovation. Green innovation is considered an important key for businesses to move towards sustainable development (Pham Anh Nguyen, 2022) and to implement green innovation, employees need to have in-depth knowledge, be able to implement recommendations, and green human resource management is a measure for managers to encourage employees to use resources sustainably.

Environmental efficiency refers to saving energy, electricity, water, minimizing the use of non-recycled materials, reducing costs, minimizing waste, and enhancing the reputation of the business (Kim et al., 2019). Environmental efficiency is the demonstration of the task of protecting the environment through the commitments of the business to achieve the environmental goals of the

business such as saving energy, using environmentally friendly materials, limiting waste discharge, etc.

Proposed Research Model

From the overview of research, review of related theories and systematization of research models on green human resource management (Rawashdeh, 2018), the impact of green human resource management on green innovation and environmental efficiency, the author has established the basis for building a theoretical analysis framework on the impact of green human resource management on green innovation and environmental efficiency of hospitals as follows.

Research Methods

Survey subjects: Managers and employees in Thai Tinh Hospital Joint Stock Company

Sampling method: The research topic selects samples for investigation using random sampling method.

Data analysis method: descriptive statistics. All operations are performed using SPSS software.

Sample size:

Number of surveyed staff:

$N = 227$ (Total number of staff as of June 2025)

Choose the confidence interval as 90%, so the deviation e is 10%

From there, we take the total N as the total number of employees as of June 2025, the accuracy is 90%, the standard error is 10%, from which we determine the minimum sample size as:

$$N = \frac{227}{1 + 227(10\%)^2} = 69,4$$

So the minimum sample size will be 70. On the other hand, the number of ballots issued will have to be larger than the minimum sample size, so the number of ballots the author must issue is 150 survey ballots, collecting 135 valid ballots.

Research Results and Discussion

To test the research hypotheses, the author builds multiple linear regression models of human resource management variables according to the dependent variables of green innovation and environmental efficiency. The results are estimated with SPSS using the least squares method.

- Hypothesis H1.1 “Recruiting green human resources” has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. The regression results show that the content “Recruiting green human resources” has a β value = 0.304 and p -value < 0.05 , meaning it has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. Hypothesis H1.1 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H1.2 “Recruiting green human resources” has a positive relationship with green innovation. The estimation results show that the p -value of the corresponding statistic is $0.002 < 0.05$. Thus, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be concluded that the variable “Recruiting green human resources” has a positive impact (positive β coefficient) on green innovation. In other words, hypothesis H1.2 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H2.1 “Green human resource training” has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. The regression results show that the content “Green human resource training” has a β value = 0.603 and p-value <0.05, meaning it has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”.

- Hypothesis H2.1 is accepted. Hypothesis H2.2 “Green human resource training” has a positive relationship with green innovation. The estimation results show that the p-value of the corresponding statistic is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be concluded that the variable Green human resource training has a positive impact (positive β coefficient) on green innovation. In other words, hypothesis H2.2 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H3.1 “Green human resource assessment” has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. The regression results show that the content “Green human resource assessment” has a β value = 0.384 and p-value <0.05, meaning it has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. Hypothesis H3.1 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H3.2 “Green human resource assessment” has a positive relationship with green innovation. The estimation results show that the p-value of the corresponding statistic is $0.010 < 0.05$. Thus, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be concluded that the variable Green human resource training has a positive impact (positive β coefficient) on green innovation. In other words, hypothesis H3.2 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H4.1 “Green human resource treatment” has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. The regression results show that the content “Green human resource treatment” has a value of $\beta = 0.354$ and p-value <0.05, meaning it has a positive impact on “Environmental efficiency”. Hypothesis H4.1 is accepted.

- Hypothesis H4.2 “Green human resource treatment” has a positive relationship with green innovation. The estimation results show that the p-value of the corresponding statistic is $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, with a confidence level of 95%, it can be concluded that the variable Green human resource training has a positive impact (positive β coefficient) on green innovation. In other words, hypothesis H4.2 is accepted.

Solutions to Promote Green Human Resource Management at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company by 2030

Innovation in Green Human Resource Recruitment

Recruitment is one of the first points of contact between employees and businesses. When done well, green recruitment will help companies reduce paperwork costs, travel costs and negative impacts on the environment. Moreover, green recruitment is determined to have a positive impact on increasing the company's environmental efficiency by creating a workforce with knowledge, skills and environmental behaviors. To achieve effectiveness, it is necessary to implement innovative solutions for green recruitment, specifically:

(i) Green job design - a basic tool of green HRM

(ii) Green HR recruitment - innovation from the start

One is to include environmental values and green recruitment standards in recruitment announcements.

Two is to use job portals, recruitment websites, social networks in recruitment and customize interviews via phone, internet and video to reduce the need for paper.

Third is to conduct recruitment interviews through technology applications to limit environmental impacts from travel activities.

Fourth, verify and evaluate each candidate's ecological knowledge, skills, and views on life values in the recruitment process. Fifth, attract and prioritize candidates with capacity, qualifications, and experience in implementing ecological projects and initiatives, and caring about the environment.

Strengthening Green Human Resource Training

Green workforce training is essential to provide additional knowledge, skills, and increase understanding and awareness of employees regarding environmental issues and sustainable development. Green workforce training is shown by research to have the most significant and significant positive impact on environmental performance and green innovation of the Company. Focusing on training green human resources will help the company have a team of workers who not only perform their professional work well but also meet the green values of work, know how to save fuel and energy during the work process, minimize environmental impact, increase initiatives and innovations at work to continuously improve environmental efficiency, which needs to be implemented in the following aspects:

- (i) Regarding training content: Green initiatives can be implemented such as: Innovating green clinic models; Developing green business strategies; Innovating green equipment; Green human resource management...
- (ii) Regarding training forms: Green training forms can be implemented such as online training, television training, distance training... with applications such as Google Class; Zoom; Trans...
- (iii) Regarding the evaluation of green human resource training programs. The evaluation of green training programs is really necessary, helping the company to have information about learning outcomes, about the application of trained knowledge and skills, about changes in work efficiency after training. The green training program can be evaluated using the Kirkpatrick model implemented before, during and after each training program.

Improving Green Workforce Assessment

To encourage employees to actively propose green initiatives, increase green innovation in the implementation process of work, thereby continuing to improve environmental efficiency and business performance, it is necessary to:

- (i) Determine a system of human resource assessment standards associated with green work.
- (ii) Regularly provide feedback to employees on the implementation process, improvement and level of achievement of their environmental protection goals.
- (iii) Send feedback results, employee assessment interviews via e-mail/internal information system of the business instead of using paper.

Investing in Green Human Resources

Green human resource treatment has a direct impact on the work results of employees, helps to create a green corporate culture, creates a favorable environment for employees to raise their awareness and behavior for the environment. Research shows that green human resource treatment has a positive impact on the environmental efficiency and green innovation of the company and this is really a big investment of the company depending on financial capacity, technology... the level of priority or expansion of activities is different. However, basically, the activities focus on the following main groups of motivational tools:

- (i) Apply fair reward and punishment policies for employees who create and effectively implement green initiatives in the company.

(ii) Organize flexible workplaces and working hours so that employees can work from anywhere; Create remote work opportunities for employees or work from home through the use of email or intranet and internet. Limit business trips by holding meetings and conferences via internet, phone and video.

(iii) Designing a green office creates space to realize green ideas in the business Organize, participate and create conditions for human resources to participate in programs and events for the environment, honoring green living

Conclusion

Through the use of appropriate qualitative and quantitative research methods along with collected secondary and primary data, the author has conducted: (i) Overview of domestic and foreign research works related to the topic of the topic to establish a theoretical framework on green human resource management at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company including: concepts and contents of green human resource management, focusing on 4 main contents: green human resource recruitment, green human resource training, green human resource assessment, green human resource treatment. On that basis, identify factors affecting green human resource management at the company.

Building a research model on green human resource management through 4 contents: green human resource recruitment, green human resource training, green human resource assessment, green human resource treatment and building hypotheses, selecting variables, and measuring scales of observations to evaluate the impact of green human resource management on green innovation and environmental efficiency of the company;

Assess the current status of green human resource management of the company by reviewing the current status of green human resource recruitment, green human resource training, green human resource assessment, and green human resource treatment by statistical and descriptive analysis combined with information and data of the case study to draw conclusions about the points of success and limitations;

Assess the current status of green human resource management of the company by reviewing the current status of green human resource recruitment, green human resource training, green human resource assessment, and green human resource treatment by statistical and descriptive analysis combined with information and data of the case study to draw conclusions about the points of success and limitations;

Verify the impact of green human resource management through the contents of green human resource recruitment, green human resource training, green human resource assessment, green human resource treatment on green innovation and environmental efficiency at the company through survey data collected from 135 questionnaires;

Propose key groups of solutions and some recommendations with reference value to promote green human resource management at Thai Think Hospital Joint Stock Company.

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